

New metrics for geographical characterization of indicators of compromise

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Abstract—The importance of Indicators of Compromise (IOC) is increasingly recognized in threat analysis, but few methodologies for IOC analysis and data enhancement have been developed. In this paper, we propose a methodology to enhance geographic feature extraction using IP address lists, a typical IOC metric. Normally, IP addresses can only represent one dimensional features of latitude and longitude, but there is a need for deeper feature extraction of geographic distribution. Therefore, this paper overlays a geographic distribution layer of DNS servers on a planar IP address list to generate a two-dimensional paired sequence of latitude and longitude and density, thereby making the geographic distribution three-dimensional and enabling more powerful characterization. Specifically, the proposed method generates a heat map consisting of latitude and longitude density and a histogram consisting of IP address density from an IP address list. Then, by simultaneously analyzing the heat map and histogram, detailed features that cannot be extracted by conventional methods can be extracted. In an evaluation experiment, the proposed method was applied to an IOC of a spam email campaign about the Russian Grizzly Steppe and Corona viruses to verify its effectiveness.

Index Terms— Indicator of compromise, geospatial analysis, DNS, density, heat map, histogram.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. TI and IoC

Threat intelligence involves collecting, analyzing, and disseminating information about potential or actual cyber threats. Its primary goal is to provide actionable insights that help organizations understand, prepare for, and respond to various security risks. This process begins with data collection from multiple sources such as open-source intelligence (OSINT), social media, dark web forums, and internal security logs. The collected data is then processed and analyzed to identify patterns, trends, and specific threats, often using advanced tools and techniques like machine learning and big data analytics. Contextualizing the analyzed data is crucial, as it provides an understanding of the potential impact, affected assets, and the likelihood of occurrence. The final step is to share this threat intelligence with relevant stakeholders within the organization, such as security teams and management, providing them with specific recommendations or steps to mitigate or respond to the identified threats.

Indicators of Compromise (IoCs) are pieces of evidence that suggest a security breach has occurred or is currently happening within an organization's network or systems. They are essential components of threat intelligence, aiding security teams in detecting, investigating, and responding to cyber threats. IoCs

can take various forms, including file hashes that uniquely identify malicious files, malicious IP addresses used for command and control servers or launching attacks, suspicious domain names associated with phishing campaigns or fraudulent websites, specific URLs used to distribute malware, email addresses involved in phishing attacks, changes to system registry keys indicating malware presence, file paths of malicious scripts, and unusual network traffic patterns suggesting data exfiltration or communication with known malicious IPs.

The importance of IoCs lies in their role in detecting and mitigating cyber threats. By identifying these indicators, security teams can quickly detect and isolate compromised systems, prevent the further spread of malware or unauthorized access, conduct forensic analysis to understand the scope and impact of a breach, and strengthen defenses against future attacks by recognizing and blocking known malicious entities. Organizations often integrate threat intelligence and IoCs into their security operations through various tools and systems. Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) systems collect and analyze security data from multiple sources, using IoCs to detect and alert on potential threats. Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems (IDPS) use IoCs to identify and block malicious activities in real-time. Threat Intelligence Platforms (TIPs) aggregate and correlate threat data from numerous sources, providing a centralized view of threat intelligence and IoCs. By leveraging threat intelligence and IoCs, organizations enhance their ability to detect, respond to, and mitigate cyber threats effectively, thereby improving their overall cybersecurity posture.

B. Geospatial Analysis

This section describes the IOC (Indicator of Compromise) indicator. It is a set of information used to describe a new threat, consisting of a domain name, a file hash value, and an IP address. Of particular importance are the IP address and the hash of the file; the IP address is very important because it indicates the origin of the traffic. Threat analysis can be divided into two categories: time series analysis and geographic analysis. In most cases, geographic analysis is very important. In most cases, geographic analysis is very important because it can detect emergencies based on the origin of the traffic. Therefore, the list of IP addresses is very important. This paper also focuses on lists of IP addresses. However, simply knowing the temporal distribution of IP addresses is not enough to extract features. In this paper, we added a layer of DNS autonomous distribution and used it to characterize the temporal distribution.

II. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

A. Data Flow

Figure 1 nominates the data flow of the proposed system. There are four arrays, A, B, C, and D. A is the IOC's IP list of addresses, and B is the DNS address list. Array B is 30 million pieces long; the A array and B are brute-forced, yielding array C. Array C is only for N IOC IP addresses, and is available as a two-dimensional array consisting of the IOC IP address and the number of DNS servers around that IP address, D. Array C is the number of DNS servers in the IOC IP list. Array D is used to create a heat map and is a pair of latitude and longitude and DNS servers. It is divided into three steps. The first step is to calculate the distance between array A and array B. Step 1 is to calculate the distance for N multiplied by M steps. Step 2 is to set a threshold value for that distance and count those that do not exceed the threshold value (0KM, 500KM, etc.). After counting, an IP address and the number of DNS servers around that IP address are created, and a two-dimensional array C is generated. Step 3 is to convert that pair of IP address and number of DNS servers into a pair IP of latitude and longitude and number of DNS servers. The overall number of steps is $N*M$ for step 1, N for step 2, and N for step 3. Therefore, since step 1 has a very large number of steps ($N*M$), we will use parallel processing applying parallel task partitioning.

Fig. 1 Dataflow of proposal system

We have measured the list of distances between DNS and IP addresses in IoC. Algorithm 1 depicts the double loop to detect the shortest distance. The program executes a double loop from lines 1 to 9 to calculate the distance between 30,285,322 DNS servers and 294 hosts in IoC. In line 5, two distances measured are compared to find the minimum distance from IoC.

For handling $30,285,322 * 294$ steps, we apply the data decomposition method for parallelizing the processing. Also, we use the python-multiprocessing module `multiproc` for speeding up the parallel processing.

Algorithm 1 Detecting Nearest DNS server

```

Input: DNS, IoC
Output: Pair{IoC, nearest(DNS)}
1: while DNS server list do
2:   Min = 100000
3:   while IoC list do
4:     Dis = distance(DNS, IoC)
5:     if Dis < Min then
6:       Min = Dis
7:     end if
8:   end while
9: end while
    
```

For calculating distance, we use GeoPy `geopy`. We wrote the code as follows:

```

DNS = (X1, Y1)
IoC = (X2, Y2)

dis = geodesic(DNS, IoC).km
    
```

GeoPy uses WGS84 (World Geodetic System 1984). By doing this, we can leverage the library of Python client for several popular geocoding web services.

Fig. 2 Task based decomposition

B. Task Based Decomposition

Regarding Figure 2, this is a parallelized version of the conversion process in Figure 1. It consists of four parts: A is a group of threads, each of which has a list of IOC IP addresses; B is a task queue, which contains a divided list of DNS servers; C is a shared data structure, which is used to share data and is controlled by mutexes; D is a two-dimensional array of IP addresses and the number of DNS servers around them. D is a two-dimensional array of IP addresses and the number of DNS servers around them.

After parallel processing is finished, this shared data structure C is converted into a pair of IP addresses and DNS servers. The parallel technique uses task parallelism. Thread A1 or A2 gets the list of DNS servers from the task queue of B and calculates the distance between IP addresses and DNS server pairs. since all threads in A have array A, it means that $N*M$ distances can be calculated even if task queue B is split.

C. Highly Concurrent Containers

The interval length of aggregation of our system is millisecond. Approximately, the granularity of histogramming is around 86,000,000 ($60 * 60 * 24 * 1000 = 86,400,000$). From our experience, it is difficult to evade lock contention to store 86,000,000 key-value into hash map in parallel. We give using concurrent hash map which is effected by lock contention. Instead, key-value can be represented by using the defining namespace such as $X1<timestamp>$, $X1<count>$ and $X2<timestamp>$ and $X2<bytes>$. Containers provided by Intel TBB offer a much higher level of concurrency, via one or both of the following methods:

1. File grained locking Multiple threads operate on the container by locking only those portions they really need to lock. As long as different threads access different portions, they can proceed concurrently.
2. Lock-free techniques Different threads account and correct for the effects of other interfering threads.

Notice that highly-concurrent containers come at a cost. They typically have higher overheads than regular STL containers. Operations on highly-concurrent containers may take longer than for STL containers. Therefore, use highly-concurrent containers when the speedup from the additional concurrency that they enable outweighs their slower sequential performance. A concurrent `_vector` T is a dynamically growable array of T. It is safe to grow a concurrent `_vector` while other threads are also operating on elements of it, or even growing it themselves.

III. MEASUREMENT

A. IoC1: Grizzly Steppe

In December 2016, the United States Department of Homeland Security (DHS) and the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) released a report named "Grizzly Steppe." This report summarized the findings of an investigation into hacking activities supported by the Russian government, particularly focusing on a series of cyber-attacks related to the 2016 U.S. presidential election. Main Targets of the Attacks:

1. Democratic National Committee (DNC): A series of attacks in 2015 and 2016 resulted in the hacking of a large volume of internal emails, which were later published through WikiLeaks.
2. Election-related Organizations: State election systems and election commissions were also targeted, with election data and voter information being the primary targets.

Methods of Attack. Phishing Attacks: Attackers used phishing

emails to steal authentication information from targets. This allowed unauthorized access to the targets' email accounts and networks. Malware Use: Specific malware (e.g., tools related to APT28 and APT29) was used to infiltrate target systems and steal information.

Remote Access Tools (RAT): Attackers used RATs to gain complete control over target systems, allowing for information gathering and further intrusion activities. Major Attack Groups are divided into two: First, APT28 (Fancy Bear): A group associated with the Russian military intelligence agency GRU, primarily involved in the attacks on the DNC. Second, APT29 (Cozy Bear): A group linked to the FSB, engaged in long-term espionage activities against a broader range of targets.

Impact of the Attacks are classified into two categories. First, Information Leaks and Publication: Hacked emails and documents were published, causing disruption in the election process and political situation. Second, Loss of Trust: The trust in the U.S. election system and political institutions was damaged, both domestically and internationally. International Tension: The incident further strained U.S.-Russia relations and increased global attention on cybersecurity.

B. IoC2: Covid-19 spam campaign

During the Covid-19 pandemic, cybercriminals exploited the situation to launch various spam email campaigns. These campaigns were designed to deceive individuals by leveraging the urgency and widespread concern caused by the pandemic.

One common method used in these campaigns was phishing. Emails impersonating government agencies or health organizations such as the CDC or WHO were sent out, claiming to provide important updates or safety guidelines. These emails contained links that directed recipients to fake login pages, where personal information could be stolen. Additionally, there were emails advertising medical products like masks, vaccines, or treatments at discounted prices. These offers were fraudulent, aiming to obtain payment information from the victims.

Another tactic involved the distribution of malware. Cybercriminals sent emails with attachments like Word documents or PDF files, which purportedly contained Covid-19 statistics or infection lists. Once opened, these attachments would infect the recipient's computer with malware. Similarly, some emails included links that, when clicked, redirected users to malicious websites where malware could be downloaded.

The content of these fraudulent emails also included fake charity appeals. These messages solicited donations for supposed Covid-19 relief efforts, using emotional stories and

Fig. 3 Heat map of Grizzly Steppe and Covid-19 spam campaign

images to elicit sympathy and encourage donations. However, the funds collected were diverted to the scammers' accounts.

Moreover, there were scams related to compensation programs. Emails posed as employers or government agencies, offering financial support or emergency pay. These messages directed recipients to provide personal information or bank details, ostensibly to process the compensation, but in reality, to steal their information.

IV. RESULTS

In this paper, we perform a geospatial analysis of DNS servers to provide a more sophisticated IoC. We cope with the open IoC of Grizzly Steppe of Russian malicious cyber activity, which is released as an open-source IoC by US-CERT. First, we designed a rapid crawling system to find DNS servers, and we detected 30285322 DNS servers in 26 hours. Based on the list of IP addresses of DNS servers which we detect, we have calculated the shortest distance from the IP address of IoC. As a result, we have detected the nearest DNS servers for each IP address of IoC.

A. Heatmap

Regarding the heatmap in Figure 3, this shows four heatmaps, A, B, C, and D. The heatmaps show latitude and longitude and their values, visualizing the final pairs of latitude and longitude and the number of DNS servers obtained in 11 and 12.

Usually, these geographic visualizations are one-dimensional and have only one layer, since they only show the latitude and longitude of IP addresses, which is difficult to characterize. However, the proposed method adds a DNS server distribution layer, which makes the characteristics stand out. For example,

when comparing A and C, if there is only one layer, IP addresses are scattered all over the place and it is almost impossible to grasp the characteristics of A and C. In this case, the number of DNS servers for each IP address is expressed as the radius of a circle, so A and C can clearly distinguish the number of DNS servers around the IP addresses of IOCs A and C can be clearly distinguished. A has one large circle in the Americas, while C has only one large circle in the Americas. Therefore, C can be characterized very clearly for the Americas, and for Europe, A has many small circles, while C has a small number of circles, thus clearly distinguishing the characteristics of the two IOCs.

The characterization is also very clear for B and D. B has small circles scattered throughout the Americas, while D has only one large circle; D has several circles in Africa, while B has almost no circles in Africa; and D has a few circles in Africa, while B has almost no circles in Africa. Thus, we can also extract very important information about which regions the attacking group is targeting.

Fig.4 Histogram of Grizzly Steppe

B. Density

Figure 4 illustrates the density for each IP address in Grizzly Steppe. The upper part of Figure 3 is roughly divided into three groups. Those with low density, those with medium density, and those with high density. They are clearly characterized. The lower side of Figure 3 shows the graph when the distance is 500 KM. It can be seen that for certain IP addresses, the density is extremely high.

Fig. 5 Histogram of Covid-19 spam campaign

Figure 5 similarly shows the relationship between IP and density in COVID19. Compared to the GS case, there is a clear separation between high and low densities. When sorted by density, a gradual increase in density can be seen even when the distance is 500 KM.

Let us discuss this with the comparison between Figures 4 and 5. So normally, if you don't consider the distribution of servers in the DNS, you end up with a list of IP addresses in the IOC. But if you include a layer of DNS, you can measure the density of servers. A mere list of IPs can be viewed from multiple angles, this time in two dimensions.

Grizzly Steppe and COVID-19 are divided into two groups when the distance is zero. One is clearly divided into two groups, one dense and one dense; even with a list of IP addresses, we can divide them into two groups within the same IOC, allowing us to characterize the geographic distribution more precisely. When the distance is set to around 500 meters, the characteristics of both IOCs are clearly visible.

Grizzly Steppe has traffic coming from relatively high-density areas, whereas Figure 5 shows that COVID-19's density increases from about the median. we can say that COVID-19's traffic is more concentrated from high-density areas. at 0 km and 500 meters. By taking multiple locations and looking at the geographic distribution from multiple angles, we can clearly distinguish the characteristics of the IOCs.

V. RELATED WORK

Pent et al. (2018) [3] evaluated VirusTotal's effectiveness against phishing websites by creating fake sites mimicking PayPal and the IRS. Zhu et al. [4](2019) proposed a data-driven

engine for online malware analysis, surveying 115 academic papers and gathering over 14,000 daily records from VirusTotal. Lewis et al. (2020) [5] introduced the Automated IP Reputation Analyzer Tool (AIPRA), leveraging reliable blacklist databases.

Karadi (2019)[6] reported on the Democratic National Committee's operations during the past election season. Malicious cyber activities by the Lazarus Group, also known as Hidden Cobra, were documented in 2018. Sinha et al. (2019) [7] characterized reputation-based blacklists[8], while PhishFarm (2020) [9] analyzed 2,380 live phishing sites classified by ten anti-phishing entities.

Bouwman et al. (2020) [10] conducted an empirical assessment of two leading commercial threat intelligence services by interviewing 14 security professionals. Zhao et al. (2021) [11] proposed HINT1, a CTI framework modeling independent relationships among heterogeneous Indicators of Compromise (IoCs). Asiri et al. (2021) [12] examined the effectiveness of IoCs in an operational technology environment. Li et al. (2021) [12] developed metrics to characterize threat intelligence data, applying them to various public and commercial sources.

Houser et al. (2022) [13] analyzed DNS hijacking using passive DNS records, applying findings to detection mechanisms. Pearce et al. (2022) [14] identified new DNS manipulation patterns with Iris, a scalable method for global DNS resolution measurement. Liu et al. (2022) [15] conducted a large-scale analysis of on-path DNS interception by recursive DNS servers, leveraging 148,378 residential and cellular IP addresses.

Augustin et al. (2023) [17] enhanced traceroute for more precise route visualization, including graphs of loops, cycles, and diamonds. Huang et al. (2023) [18] introduced a new traceroute implementation for large-scale topology discovery of the entire /24 address space.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a multidimensional and multifaceted feature extraction method by superimposing the density of the geographic distribution of DNS servers on the geographic distribution of IP addresses of IOCs, which previously could only be captured in one or two dimensions. By overlaying a density layer of the geographic distribution of DNS servers on a 2:1 distribution based on latitude and longitude calculated from IP addresses, information that was previously only a list of IP addresses can now be made multi-dimensional and features can be captured in two dimensions.

Our technique allows features to be extracted from geographic location of movement longitude and server density data. Originally, IP addresses in IOCs were only a list, and it was difficult to capture their spread and characteristics, which made it impossible to understand the trends and characteristics of attack groups behind the IOCs and to accurately understand the threats they pose.

This method investigates the enumeration of IP addresses from multiple angles, and we developed a method to create heat

maps and histograms by superimposing the density of DNS servers on their geographic distribution. It is also possible to create a histogram by assigning a density to the IP addresses themselves.

The proposed method created both a heatmap and a histogram. The evaluation experiments were conducted on IOCs from the Grizzly Steps and COVID-19 spam campaigns. For each IOC, the geographic distribution of about 32 million DNS servers was overlaid to create heatmaps and histograms. Two densities were created, one within 1 km of the IP address of each IOC and the other within 50 km.

For grizzly steppe, we found that the features were highly visible within 1 kilometer; for COVID-19, we were able to successfully extract the features by increasing the distance and measuring the density within 500 kilometers. The proposed method is unique in that it can be applied to any IOC, regardless of the nature of the attack. Our future task is to verify the effectiveness of the proposed method by applying it to various attacks.

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